

Research Data Champions program

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Self-assessment resource list

This is a list of resources provided for further learning about various aspects of Research Data Management. Many of the links provided are to the Research Data Management library guide.

General Research Data Management knowledge

- Information on [research data](#) from the RDM guide.
- Information on [data management planning](#) (RDM guide).
- An intro to the [FAIR principles](#) (RDM guide).
- [Make your data more FAIR](#) from Curtin Library (PDF).
- More information on [FAIR data](#) from the ARDC.
- [Where to find eResearch support](#) within Curtin.
- [Further training resources](#) (RDM guide).

Organisation and Retention

- Information on [storage and access](#) (RDM guide).
- Information on [data format and organisation](#) (RDM guide).
- Information on [documentation and description](#) (RDM guide).
- Information on [retention and preservation](#) (RDM guide).

Analysis and Versioning

- Information on [data analytics and tools](#) from Uniskills.
- Information on [working with research software](#) from ARDC.
- Information on [versioning](#) (RDM guide).

Data Sharing

- Information on [data ownership](#) (RDM guide).
- Information on [sharing and publishing](#) (RDM guide).
- Information on [citation](#) (RDM guide).
- Information on [reusing data](#) (RDM guide).
- Information on [funder data sharing policies](#) (RDM guide).

Data Ethics

- Information on [data ethics](#) from ARDC (PDF file).
- Information on [sensitive data](#) from ARDC.
- Information on [indigenous data](#) from ARDC.
- the *Code of Ethics for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Research* from AIATSIS.
- [Key principles on Indigenous data sovereignty and governance](#) from Maïam nayri Wingara